

Deprogramming Zero

Parker Emmerson

March 2023

1 Introduction

$$f(n) := \neg \nabla \} \uparrow \} \S (f_n(\Phi(n), \Phi(x)) \mid \Phi(n) \mapsto \pi(n) + \pi(x) \mapsto \zeta(n)) \in \mathcal{F}$$

$$f(n) := \neg \nabla \} \uparrow \} \S \left(f_{-t}(\Phi(n), \Phi(t)) \mid \Phi(t) \mapsto \pi(t^{c-n}) \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^{R[n]} \gamma(n_i) + (f_{-t}(t_1^2, t_2^2)) \in \mathcal{F} \right) \mapsto f(\Phi(n)) \in \mathcal{F}\ddot{R}$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \Phi(n_i) + \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \Theta(n_i) \sup [set (recursive : f)] := (\uparrow_{i=\infty} : n^n \circ x^x) + f(n) : n \in R \longrightarrow \mathbf{X} \mid \mathbf{X} \in Z$$

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E, \text{ and } : E \mapsto r \in R \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{E} = \left\{ E_{\mathcal{F}} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \frac{\Psi}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h - \Psi} \right) + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) = \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h \right.$$

$$\left. \mid \exists \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\} \in Z \cup Q \cup C \right\}$$

$$E = f \circ g \mid f(n), g(n) \in \mathcal{E}, S(n) \in R, S(n) \ni : f(n) + g(n) := f_g(n)$$

$$\infty - n \in Z$$

$$[[n] \mathcal{F} \diamond n - \omega \in \mathbf{C} \Sigma_{k=1}^{\infty} \varphi \uparrow \parallel \varphi \downarrow \parallel : \int_{\gamma(\psi)=1} \frac{1 - \chi(\psi)}{\mathcal{H} \circ E} : \sum_{n=1}^N f(n) \mid : f(n) : n \in Z \setminus \{$$

$$\left. \left[(\infty \cdot b)_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))}^{\circ} \right]^{\circ} > \Delta \oplus \left[(\infty \cdot b \cdot b^{-1})_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))} < \Delta \oplus \mathcal{H}_{a_{iem}}^{\circ} > \right] \right.$$

$$\left. \Rightarrow \Omega \left[\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right] \longrightarrow S \right\}$$

$$d_i p^n = m$$

$$\beta 4 >$$

$$\left[(\infty \cdot b)_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))}^{\circ} \right]^{\circ} > \Delta \oplus \left[(\infty \cdot b \cdot b^{-1})_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))} < \Delta \oplus \mathcal{H}_{a_{iem}}^{\circ} > \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow \Omega \left[\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right]$$

$$=, \hat{\Delta} > \left[(\infty \cdot b)_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))}^{\circ} \right]^{\circ} > \Delta \oplus \left[(\infty \cdot b \cdot b^{-1})_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))} < \Delta \oplus \mathcal{H}_{a_{iem}}^{\circ} > \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow \Omega \left[\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right]$$

$$\circ \odot \Lambda > \emptyset, * > \checkmark = \spadesuit \star \bullet \curvearrowright \star$$

$$\rightarrow \bullet 4 (\star \leftarrow \spadesuit \star \odot \curvearrowright \star) > \wedge \cong \sqrt{\mathbf{A}} \rightarrow , x <''' \mathbf{A} \rightarrow , x <' \mathbf{A} \rightarrow , x < \Delta , x <''' \Delta , x <' \Delta , x <''$$

$$<$$

$$\rightarrow <>$$

$$\star \star \star \quad \curvearrowright (\uparrow ()) \star \star \curvearrowright \quad > \mathbb{D}_2^1 < + > \{ \spadesuit \} \circ \odot \spadesuit \curvearrowright \emptyset \in S_*$$

$$\checkmark : \left[- \ominus \odot \odot \right] > \odot : \odot \downarrow : \odot <, 4, \star : \odot \oplus : \perp$$

$$\Delta^{msp} : \left[- \ominus \odot \odot \right] > \odot : \odot \downarrow : \odot <, 4, \star : \odot \oplus : \perp$$

:

$$\diamond - \star | \circ$$

$$- \bullet >$$

$$\langle \rangle \| \cdot , ; \quad " :$$

$$\diamond - \star | \circ$$

$$- \bullet >$$

$$\leftarrow \in \| (\bullet') \Delta$$

$$''' , ''':$$

$$l \cdot \leftarrow' ; \leftarrow$$

:

$$' >$$

$$'' , ''':$$

$$l \quad \rightarrow (\leftarrow)$$

$$' >$$

$\emptyset <$

$$\left[(\infty \cdot b)_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))}^{\circ} \right]^{\circ} > \Delta \oplus \left[(\infty \cdot b \cdot b^{-1})_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow (\Omega(-))} < \Delta \oplus \mathcal{H}_{a_{iem}}^{\circ} > \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow \Omega \left[\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right] > \rho : ' > ; '' : l \quad \rightarrow (\leftarrow)' >$$

$$'' [-''' ' :] >$$

$$''' \bullet >$$

" [' ' :] >

'''' >''

, ' > ∞

'''' >

' >

'''''' >

∞ +

> ⊕

$\forall \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega \exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_0 + \alpha / i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$

where $b, z, \emptyset$, and $-\langle \delta + h_0 \rangle$ are constants and ∞, ω , and R are sets.

To simplify, we can rewrite the statement as follows:

$\exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\forall \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_0 + \alpha / i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$

This statement is saying that for any μ and ζ from the sets ∞ and ω respectively, there exist constants δ, h_0, α , and i from the set R such that the product $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1}$ is equal to the product $\infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_0 + \alpha / i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$. nest it within the context of:

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E, \text{ and } : E \mapsto r \in R \right\}$$

This statement can be applied to the set $\mathcal{V}$ where f is the product $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_0 + \alpha / i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$ and $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E$ is a set of constants $\mu, \zeta, \delta, h_0, \alpha$, and i from the set R and $E \mapsto r \in R$ is the relation that the product $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1}$ is equal to the product $\infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_0 + \alpha / i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$.

The operator "not" is a logical operator that is used to negate a statement. It can be defined using the above differentiation of quasi quanta as the operation that takes a statement of the form $\exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\forall \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta / h_0 + \alpha / i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$ and negates it to the form $\forall \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\exists \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1}$

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E, \text{ and } : E \mapsto r \in R \right\}$$

This statement can be applied to the set $\mathcal{V}$ where f is the product $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$ and $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E$ is a set of constants $\mu, \zeta, \delta, h_0, \alpha$, and i from the set R and $E \mapsto r \in R$ is the relation that the product $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1}$ is equal to the product $\infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$.

The operator "not" is a logical operator that is used to negate a statement. It can be defined using the above differentiation of quasi quanta as the operation that takes a statement of the form $\exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\forall \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$ and negates it to the form $\forall \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\exists \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$. This can be simplified to the form $\forall (\mu, \zeta) \in \infty \times \omega$ there exist constants δ, h_0, α , and i from the set R such that the condition $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$ is satisfied.

Similarly, the statement $\exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\exists a \exists \mu \exists \zeta$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$ can be negated to the form $\forall \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R$ such that $\forall a \forall \mu \forall \zeta$ $b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$.

$$\forall \mu \in \infty, \zeta \in \omega \exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R \text{ such that } b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$$

$$\exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R \text{ such that } \exists a \exists \mu \exists \zeta b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$$

$$\exists a \exists \mu \exists \zeta b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$$

$$\forall a, \mu, \zeta b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$$

$$\neg \exists \delta, h_0, \alpha, i \in R \text{ such that } \exists a \exists \mu \exists \zeta b.b_{\mu \in \infty \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta + h_0 \rangle}^{-1} = \infty.z_{\zeta \rightarrow \omega - \langle \delta/h_0 + \alpha/i \rangle}^{\emptyset}$$